

The optimization of process parameters of three-dimensional needled composites based on ANN and GA

Yunchao Qi

Application and technology of needled composites

Application

The unique process characteristics of needling materials make the fiber structure inside the materials very complex, which makes the mechanical properties of the materials more dispersive.

Question: The needled process parameters are numerous, so how to find the best process parameters?

BP neural network diagram

A surrogate model for optimizing process parameters of three dimensional needled preforms of composites was established based on back propagation (BP) neural network combing with improved genetic algorithm.

Genetic algorithm diagram

The genetic strategy and optimization strategy of genetic algorithm were improved.

Optimization results

Genetic algorithm fitness changes with genetic algebra

Stiffness properties of materials before and after optimization

Stiffness properties	No optimization results(GPa)	Optimization results(GPa)
E1	57.51	64.1120
E3	30.92	45.8
G12	14.09	14.38
G23	9.856	9.560
fitness	28.31	33.46

Process parameters of the optimized material

Material parameters	Needling depth(mm)	Needling density(needle/cm ²)	Needle way x(mm)	Needle way y(mm)
Results	8.459	13.93	1.015	1.693